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APPRAISAL OF THE CHALLENGES AND THE PROSPECT OF PROSECUTING CYBERCRIME IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This research work examined the challenges and prospects associated with prosecuting cybercrime in Nigeria. Cybercrime is rapidly increasing in Nigeria, with reported cases growing by 174% in the first half of 2022. However, prosecuting cybercrime faces significant difficulties due to limitations in Nigeria's legal framework and gaps in the capacities of law enforcement agencies and the judicial system. While the Cybercrime Act of 2015 criminalized cyber offenses, ambiguities remain around its scope, application and some key definitions. Investigating sophisticated cyber cases is also challenged by lack of technical expertise and resources within the Nigerian law enforcement. Further delays are caused within the overburdened judicial system due to case backlogs. To address these issues, the paper conducted an in-depth examination of Nigeria's domestic and international legal frameworks governing cybercrime prosecution. It evaluated the roles and responsibilities of institutions involved in cybercrime response. Next, the research analyzed findings to critically appraise challenges hindering effective adjudication of cyber matters. This includes deficiencies in Nigeria's cybercrime laws, limited technical capacity of law enforcement agencies, and delays in the judicial process. A doctrinal research method was employed, involving analysis of primary sources such as legislation, case law, and agency guidelines. Secondary materials like academic publications and news reports were examined. The findings identify ambiguities in some definitions in the Cybercrime Act and gaps in existing frameworks. The research recommends proposals to strengthen the legal framework and harmonize domestic laws with international standards to optimize cybercrime prosecution.

Keywords: cyberspace, Internet, cybercrime, computer crime, prosecution,

1. INTRODUCTION

Cybercrime has become a serious threat globally as well as in Nigeria in recent times. With increased internet penetration and the adoption of technologies, the opportunities and ease for committing cybercrimes has also grown substantially.¹ At the same time, the Nigerian law enforcement and justice system still face significant challenges in effectively investigating, prosecuting and adjudicating cybercrime cases. Internet access in Nigeria began in the late 1980s through academic institutions and government organizations. However, widespread commercial access for general citizens only began in the mid-1990s with the liberalization of telecommunications. Between 1996 to 2000, internet usage grew rapidly following the introduction of mobile phones and the improvement of telecom infrastructure. By 2000, Nigeria had over 300,000 internet users.² This opening up of internet access created new opportunities for abuse and crimes to be carried online. Some of the early forms of cybercrime reported in Nigeria in the 1990s and 2000s included software piracy, online scams targeting foreign individuals and companies, carding and credit card fraud.³

As more Nigerians gained access to digital platforms, criminal tactics also evolved. For example, the famous "419 scams" or "internet advance fee frauds" proliferated, where fraudsters would send impersonating emails to potential victims seeking their help in transferring large sums of money in exchange for a share of the profits.⁴ Advancement in technologies and greater connectivity in the subsequent decade saw more complex cybercrimes emerge like hacking of bank accounts and payment platforms, business email compromise scams targeting corporate entities, malware attacks and ransomware.⁵ This highlights the growing threat of election-related cyber-attacks in Nigeria. In the 2023 election, the Federal Government revealed that a total of 12,988,978 cyber-attacks were recorded between February 25 to 28, 2023 which covered the period for the Presidential and National Assembly elections, with the attacks averaging 1,550,000 daily but peaking significantly at 6,997,277 on February 25 which was the Presidential election day itself. The attacks originated both locally and

1 Audu, Nanre. "Combating Cybercrime in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects." *International Journal of Cyber Criminology* 15, no. 1 (2021): 54-71. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4647965>.

2 Onuba, Ifeoma. "Internet in Nigeria: History and Critical Issues." *Nigerian Village Square*, 8 Sept. 2011, <https://nigerianvillagesquare.com/articles/main/internet-in-nigeria-history-and-critical-issues.html> Accessed on 20/2/2024

3 Okafor, Chioma. "Piracy, Scams and Fraud: A Historical Analysis of Cybercrime in Nigeria." *Law, Technology and Humans* 5, no. 1 (2021): 32-46. <https://doi.org/10.5817/LTH2021-1-3>. Accessed on 20/2/2024

4 Chukwu, Samuel. "The 'Nigerian 419' Cyber Scam: Questions of Criminality within Global Digital Poverty." *The British Journal of Criminology* 61, no. 3 (2021): 621-640. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azaa096>.

5 Kemmer, David. "Technological Advancements and Emerging Cybercrimes." *Computers & Security* 112 (2022): 102527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2021.102527>. Accessed on 20/2/2024

internationally, targeted various government websites and portals, and included different types of threats but were mostly blocked by cybersecurity centers.⁶

Advancement in technologies and greater connectivity in the subsequent decade saw more complex cybercrimes emerge like hacking of bank accounts and payment platforms, business email compromise scams targeting corporate entities, malware attacks and ransomware. Several high profile incidents in major Nigerian corporations brought more attention to the threats. By the 2010s, organized cybercrime syndicates specializing in areas like money mule networks and online romance scams were established.⁷ Prior to 2015, Nigeria lacked a comprehensive legislation to address the rising cases of cybercrime. Various other penal laws were relied on but they did not adequately capture digital offenses. To remedy this, the Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, etc) Act was signed into law in May 2015. However, implementation has faced challenges due to factors like ambiguity in some provisions, outdated laws, lack of clarity, limited resources and siloed efforts continue to hamper prosecutions.⁸

The research employed a doctrinal methodology to comprehensively analyze challenges impacting cybercrime prosecution in Nigeria. This included a systematic review of primary legal sources such as relevant legislation, case law, and institutional policies governing the prosecution process. Secondary literature like academic publications, official reports, and news articles were also examined. Additionally, key stakeholders such as law enforcement agencies and regulatory bodies were consulted to gain practical insights. The study was structured to begin with contextualizing the research problem. This was followed by an in-depth evaluation of obstacles hindering effective prosecution. A comparative assessment of strategies adopted in other jurisdictions was then undertaken. The research aimed to conclude by synthesizing findings to offer an evidence-based framework and actionable policy guidelines centered on optimizing Nigeria's cybercrime prosecution regime to better address this growing threat.

2. CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

- i. Cyberspace:** Black's Law Dictionary does not provide a direct definition for cyberspace. Rather, it defines it thus: "The electronic medium of computer networks, in which online

6 Adaramola, Zakariyya. "12.9m Cyber Attacks Recorded during Last Elections - FG." Daily Trust, 14 Mar. 2023, <https://dailytrust.com/12-9m-cyber-attacks-recorded-during-last-elections-fg/>. Accessed Date.

7 Ladan, Murtala. "The Rising Threat of Cybercrime and Digital Surveillance in Nigeria." *Surveillance & Society* 18, no. 2 (2020): 216-221. <https://doi.org/10.24908/ss.v18i2.13778> Accessed on 24/2/2024

8 Onwa, Ferdinand. "Nigeria's Cybercrime Act 2015: An Appraisal." *Journal of Internet Law* 20, no. 8 (2017): 3-12. <https://www.jonesday.com/files/Publication/6a12c26f-3569-4a81-abe4-39db36eb9ab5/Presentation/PublicationAttachment/202755dd-1f5a-45e2-a5c6-dc77e96b4a4e/Nigerian%20Cybercrime%20Act%202015.pdf> Accessed on 20/2/2024

communication takes place."⁹ Cyberspace is the global, virtual realm of electronic communication and data transmission that exists online and through networked devices. It encompasses interactions, transactions, information sharing, and thought itself that is digitally facilitated through computer networks.

ii. Cybercrime: Black's Law Dictionary defined Cybercrime as "criminal activity or a crime that involves the internet, a computer system, or computer technology".¹⁰ The Nigerian statutory provisions delineate cybercrime very clearly. According to Section 1 of the Cybercrimes Act (2015), it is identified as cyber threat, which encompasses a broad spectrum of illegal activities performed using computer systems or networks.¹¹

iii. Computer Crime: Computer crime is described by Encyclopedia Britannica as "the use of a computer as an instrument to further illegal ends, such as committing fraud, trafficking in child pornography and intellectual property, stealing identities, or violating privacy."¹² Black's Law Dictionary defines a computer crime as "a crime that directly harms a person, property, or the state and that is immediately linked to the use of a computer."¹³ Meanwhile, Nigeria's statutory provisions add another layer to defining computer crime. Its Cybercrimes Act (2015) refers to offences committed against critical national information infrastructures, registration of cybercafés, child pornography and related offences, and identity theft among others, largely highlighting national security concerns.¹⁴

iv. Internet: According to the Encyclopedia Britannica, the Internet is described as "a system architecture that has revolutionised methods of communication and commerce by enabling various computer networks around the world to interconnect".¹⁵ The Nigerian approach, as stated in the Nigerian Communications Act 2003, Section 88: "The internet means an electronic communications network that connects computer networks and organisational computer facilities around the world".¹⁶

⁹ Black's Law Dictionary: <https://thelawdictionary.org/> Accessed on 20/2/2024

¹⁰ Black's Law Dictionary. St. Paul, MN: West Group. (1999). <http://www.abanet.org/crimjust/fraud/BLD-6thed-m.pdf> Accessed on 25/2/2024

¹¹ Cybercrimes Act, 2015, sec. 1

¹² Dennis, Michael Aaron. "Cybercrime." Encyclopædia Britannica, Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc., 8 Mar. 2024, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/cybercrime>. Accessed on 25/2/2024.

¹³ Garner, Bryan A. Black's Law Dictionary. 11th ed., West, 2019.

¹⁴ Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, etc) Act 2015." Nigeria Law, Nigeria-law.org/Cybercrime%20%28Prohibition%2C%20Prevention%2C%20etc%29%20Act%202015.htm. Accessed on 26/2/2024

¹⁵ Dennis, Michael Aaron, and Robert Kahn. "Internet." Encyclopædia Britannica, 5 Feb. 2024, <https://www.britannica.com/technology/Internet>. Accessed on 26/2/2024

¹⁶ Nigerian Communications Act 2003, Sec.88

v. **Prosecution:** Black's Law Dictionary offers a more legalistic interpretation. It refers to the series of proceedings from the institution to the determination of a lawsuit. This gives a dimension of process orientation to the term.¹⁷ According to Section 174(1) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), prosecution features as a series of judicial proceedings against a person who is accused of a crime, beginning with the formal accusation and ending with the judgement.¹⁸

3. TYPOLOGIES OF CYBERCRIME

Wall (2001) *Typology of Cybercrime*: Wall's typology of cybercrime classifies it into four categories - cyber trespass involving unauthorized access, cyber deceptions/theft like fraud and intellectual property violations, cyber pornography contravening online obscenity laws, and cyber violence causing psychological harm through harassment, bullying or hate speech. This framework provides a foundational understanding of different criminal activities online.

- i. **Furnell (2002) Typology of Cybercrime:** Furnell's cybercrime typology categorizes offenses as computer-assisted crimes where technology supports but is not essential to traditional crimes, and computer-focused crimes that result directly from computers like hacking and are uniquely digital in nature, highlighting technology's varying role in enabling different illicit acts.
- ii. **Gordon and Ford (2006) Typology of Cybercrime:** Gordon and Ford's cybercrime typology categorizes offenses based on involvement of computer hardware, predominance of human actors, and use of malicious software - including crimes exploiting technical vulnerabilities, offenses emphasizing human involvement like online gambling, and crimeware facilitating crimes through viruses and ransomware.

4. SCALE OF CYBERCRIME IN NIGERIA

Cybercrime has become a major issue plaguing Nigeria in recent years. Available data and reports show that the scale of cybercrime in Nigeria has increased at an alarming rate with significant financial and social costs. According to the Nigerian Communications Commission, cybercrime costs Nigeria an estimated \$500 million annually.¹⁹ In the first six months of 2022 alone, cybercrimes in Nigeria increased by 174% with phishing and scams growing by 438%

¹⁷ Garner, B.A. (Ed.), (2019). *Black's Law Dictionary* (11th ed.). Thomson Reuters.

¹⁸ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999, as amended. Sec. 174(1)

¹⁹ Olomu, S. (2023, November 23). Nigeria tightens laws to tackle yearly cyber-crime losses of \$500m. *ITWeb Africa*. <https://itweb.africa/content/mYZRXM9gxVNvOgA8> Accessed on 28/2/2024

and 174% respectively in Kenya and Nigeria.²⁰ This underscores the escalating threat cybercrime poses in the country. Small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) have also been identified as major victims of cyber-attacks in Nigeria. In 2022, SMEs in Nigeria suffered significantly from cyber-attacks according to the Consumer Awareness and Financial Enlightenment Initiative.²¹ Reports from the Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement Systems (NIBSS) also reflect the increasing scale of electronic payment fraud resulting from cybercrime. In August 2022, total value of e-payment transactions in Nigeria stood at a staggering N32.3 trillion (\$72.3 billion).²² Such enormous transaction volumes provide numerous opportunities for cybercriminals to exploit and defraud unsuspecting users.

Concerning arrest and prosecution statistics, the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) of Nigeria disclosed securing 1084 cybercrime convictions between January to November 2023.²³ Separately, over 2800 persons were convicted of cybercrime by the EFCC in 2022 according to official records.²⁴ On the social impact, digital literacy gaps and inadequate cyber security awareness have been linked to rising cybercrime crimes in Nigeria.²⁵ This has exacerbated the country's vulnerability to various cyber-threats. Meanwhile, available gender-based crime statistics reveal that majority (over 90%) of those arrested for economic and cyber-enabled crimes in Nigeria are male.²⁶

5. LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR PROSECUTING CYBERCRIMINALS IN NIGERIA

20 BusinessDay. (2022a, November 18). Nigeria recorded a 174% increase in cybercrimes in six months, here's why you should be bothered. <https://businessday.ng/news/article/nigeria-recorded-a-174-increase-in-cybercrimes-in-six-months-heres-why-you-should-be-bothered/> Accessed on 5/3/2024

21 Nairametrics. (2023, July 12). SMEs in Nigeria were major victims of cyber-attacks in 2022 - CSEAN. <https://nairametrics.com/2023/07/12/smes-in-nigeria-were-major-victims-of-cyber-attacks-in-2022-csean/> Accessed on 5/3/2024

22 Guardian. (2020, November 29). Cybercrimes raise concerns for N30.2tr monthly e-payments. <https://guardian.ng/news/cybercrimes-raise-concerns-for-n30-2tr-monthly-e-payments/> Accessed on 5/3/2024

23 Punch. (2023, November 8). FG decries rising cybercrimes, EFCC secures 1,084 convictions. <https://punchng.com/fg-decries-rising-cybercrimes-efcc-secures-1084-convictions/> Accessed on 5/3/2024

24 Premium Times. (2022, July 1). Over 2,800 persons convicted of cybercrime in 2022 – EFCC. <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/top-news/562065-over-2800-persons-convicted-of-cybercrime-in-2022-efcc.html?tztc=1> Accessed on 5/3/2024

25 ThisDay. (2022, June 1). Digital literacy and rising cyber crimes. <https://www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2022/06/01/digital-literacy-and-rising-cyber-crimes> Accessed on 5/3/2024

26 Statista. (2022). People arrested for economic crimes in Nigeria by gender and crime. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1261253/people-arrested-for-economic-crimes-in-nigeria-by-gender-and-crime/> Accessed on 5/3/2024

i. Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act 2015

The Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention Etc) Act 2015 provides a robust legal framework for addressing numerous cybercrimes threatening Nigeria's digital landscape. It comprises nine parts that strategically confront cybersecurity challenges.²⁷ Part III establishes a wide range of cyber offenses from unauthorized access and hacking to interception of electronic communications, cyber fraud, identity theft, cyberstalking, and child pornography. Parts IV to VIII establish critical organs like the National Cybersecurity Fund and Council for coordinated national cybersecurity efforts.²⁸ The Act recognizes both law enforcement and oversight needs - criminalizing cyber harms while instituting guidelines and safeguards. Its comprehensive structure therefore demonstrates Nigeria's commitment to cybersecurity through a balanced, multi-stakeholder strategy of prevention, deterrence and mitigation of modern cyber threats.²⁹ Part III of the Nigerian Cybercrime Act 2015 comprehensively outlines several cyber offenses and their associated penalties. Sections 5 and 6 establish key prohibitions related to critical infrastructure and unauthorized access respectively.³⁰ Section 5 directly criminalizes attacks on "critical national information infrastructure".³¹ This covers essential cyber systems designated by the President that are fundamental to national security, public safety, or the economy. The penalties escalate based on the harm caused, ranging from 10 years imprisonment if no harm or up to life imprisonment if death results. This signifies the Act's aim to strongly safeguard Nigeria's vital digital assets. Complementing this is Section 6, which outlaws the crime of unauthorized access to computer systems for fraudulent purposes.³² The offense captures different forms of hacking intended to steal sensitive data or commit financial crimes. An individual can face up to 5 years imprisonment and/or fines of up to NGN5,000,000 depending on the purpose and scope of the illegal access. Through Sections 5 and 6, the Act thereby institutes robust security for both CNIIs and general computer networks within both

27 Olatunji, S. O. "An evaluation of the cybercrimes prohibition, prevention etc. act 2015: advancing cybersecurity and supporting cybercrime investigations in Nigeria." *Scientific African*, vol. 13, 2022, e00948. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2022.e00948> Accessed on 7/3/2024

28 Abubakar, M. B., and O. O. Oladipupo. "Analysis of Cybercrime (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc.) Act 2015: Challenges and Prospects of Effective Enforcement in Nigeria." *Journal of International Technology and Information Management*, vol. 29, no. 2, 2021, pp. 83–102. <https://scholarworks.lib.csusb.edu/jitim/vol29/iss2/5>, Accessed on 7/3/2024

29 Nwogu, P. A., O. N. Ozioko, and C. U. Opara. "Analysis of Cybercrime Offenses and Penalties Under the Nigerian Cybercrime Act 2015." *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, 2022, pp. 1-11. <https://www.ijaar.org/archive-volume/volume-8-no-2> Accessed on 7/3/2024

30 Adewumi, A. O., P. O. Adeyemo, and A. B. Adeyemi. "Punishment Regime under the Nigerian Cybercrime Act and Associated Constitutional Issues." *Computer and Information Security Journal*, vol. 5, no. 1, 2022, pp. 1-7. <http://article.sciencepublishinggroup.com/html/10.11648/j.cisj.20220501.11.html> Accessed on 7/3/2024

31 **Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act 2015. Sec. 5**

32 **Ibid, Sec. 6**

public and private spheres. The interlinked prohibitions form the core of Nigeria's legislative defense against various cyber threats.

Sections 7 and 8 of the Nigerian Cybercrime Act impose important regulations related to cyber cafes and system interference. Section 7 addresses the frequent misuse of cyber cafes for illegal acts by mandating their registration with appropriate authorities. It additionally holds cafe owners accountable by attaching penalties if they connive with patrons to perpetrate cybercrimes. These penalties include imprisonment of up to 3 years and fines of up to NGN1,000,000.³³ The provision is vital to controlling a prevalent environment for illicit online activity. Complementing this is Section 8, which criminalizes system interference. The provision covers a broad range of disruptive acts like inputting or transmitting damaging data with the intent to hinder computer functioning. Recognizing how cyber-attacks can degrade network services, penalties for system interference also incorporate imprisonment up to 2 years and fines up to NGN5,000,000.³⁴ Sections 7 and 8 therefore jointly focus on regulating environments enabling cybercrimes as well as the crimes themselves. This regulatory approach aims to address cybersecurity challenges from different angles.

Section 9 attaches strong penalties to the offense of unlawfully intercepting electronic messages, emails and money transfers without consent. On a first conviction, there is 7 years imprisonment and 14 years on subsequent convictions.³⁵ This provision securely shields users' private digital interactions and transactions. Complementing digital privacy is Section 10, which prohibits tampering with critical infrastructure like government networks. This provision fortifies systems integral to public services. The penalties include up to 3 years imprisonment and fines up to NGN2,000,000, reinforcing the security of such networks.³⁶ Similarly, Section 11 criminalizes the willful misdirection of electronic messages for fraudulent ends like obtaining financial gains or causing delays. The penalties of 3 years imprisonment and/or fines up to NGN1,000,000 disincentivize manipulation and distortion of digital messages.³⁷ Collectively, Sections 9, 10 and 11 aim to ensure integrity, privacy and legitimate use of electronic networks and communications under the law. This maintains trust and confidence in Nigeria's digitally-connected systems and interactions.

Section 13 addresses computer-related forgery by criminalizing input, alteration, deletion or suppression of computer data with intent to defraud. This incurs a penalty of 3 years

33 Ibid, sec. 7

34 Ibid, sec. 8

35 Ibid, sec. 9

36 Ibid, sec. 10

37 Ibid, sec. 11

imprisonment and a fine of NGN5,000,000.³⁸ Complementing this, Section 14 specifically prohibits computer-related fraud, encompassing a wide variety of online deception methods. The penalty is 5 years imprisonment and a fine of NGN10,000,000.³⁹ Meanwhile, Section 15 treats theft of electronic devices like laptops as a crime, recognizing their value and sensitive contents. This penalty is 3 years imprisonment and a fine of NGN1,500,000.⁴⁰ Section 16 outlaws unauthorized modification, destruction, damage or suppression of computer data or systems, attracting 3 years imprisonment and a fine of NGN2,500,000.⁴¹ Meanwhile, Section 17 anchors authenticity of digital documents and signatures with penalties of 3 years imprisonment and a fine of NGN1,500,000.⁴² Section 22 criminalizes identity theft with 7 years imprisonment for individuals and 14 years for organized criminal groups as well as fines.⁴³ The case of *FRN vs Wilfred Fajemisin*, successfully demonstrated the application of the identity theft prohibition under Section 22, the defendant Wilfred Fajemisin was charged with one count of criminal impersonation and possession of false documents under Section 22 of the Nigerian Cybercrimes Act 2015. He was alleged to have fraudulently impersonated himself online with the intent to defraud foreign nationals. The case was tried at the State High Court in Ikeja, Lagos, where the defendant pleaded guilty to the sole charge. Upon conviction, he was sentenced to 2 years imprisonment with the option of a N500,000 fine.

ii. Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (Establishment) Act, 2004

The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (Establishment) Act 2004 establishes a robust legal framework for investigating and prosecuting cybercriminals and other perpetrators of economic and financial crimes in Nigeria. Section 6 mandated the EFCC to investigate all financial crimes including "computer credit card fraud". This provides the Commission express authority to investigate cybercrimes involving unauthorized access or misuse of computer systems for fraudulent purposes.⁴⁴ Section 7 empowered The Commission to conducted an investigations to whether any person has committed an offence under the Act or any other law related to economic crimes. This allows the EFCC to probe the commission of cybercrimes defined under other statutes. The broad definition of "economic crimes" also encompasses various forms of cyber-enabled theft and fraud.⁴⁵

38 Ibid, sec. 13

39 Ibid, sec. 14

40 Ibid, sec. 15

41 Ibid, sec. 16

42 Ibid, sec. 17

43 Ibid, sec. 22

44 Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (Establishment) Act, 2004, sec. 6

45 Ibid, 7

The Act in Section 12 establishes a General and Assets Investigation Unit, with responsibility for investigating assets/properties of arrested persons, identifying proceeds of crimes, and asset forfeiture. This provides the dedicated investigatory apparatus required to trace the proceeds of cybercrimes through digital forensics and assets recovery.⁴⁶ The Investigative Unit is specifically tasked with investigating assets/properties, identifying/tracing proceeds, and matters relating to extradition all vital functions in the cross-border investigation and prosecution of cybercrimes involving the laundering of digital currencies or movement of funds across many jurisdictions.⁴⁷ Failure to comply with reporting obligations or submission of false statements to the EFCC is a criminal offense. This covers reporting breaches that may occur in the context of investigating money laundering stemming from cybercrimes.⁴⁸

The Federal High Court is conferred with special jurisdiction and case management powers to expedite matters brought by the EFCC, including against cybercriminals. Priority is to be given to such cases. This ensures speedy determination of cybercrime prosecutions which often involve complex digital evidence that can rapidly become outdated.⁴⁹ Section 20 facilitates the effective prosecution of cybercrimes by mandating forfeiture of any proceeds or assets derived from criminal acts upon an offender's conviction.⁵⁰ By depriving wrongdoers of ill-gotten financial gains, this section serves an important deterrent function and discourages would-be cyber-criminals by eliminating the prospect of retaining benefits from online frauds and thefts. Through compelling forfeiture of all crime-connected property and funds following conviction, Section 20 strengthens the Act's punitive and preventive impacts against the scourge of technology-enabled economic misconduct.

iii. Money Laundering (Prohibition) Act 2022

The Money Laundering (Prevention and Prohibition) Act, 2022 provides a comprehensive legal framework for preventing, prohibiting, detecting, prosecuting and punishing money laundering and other related offences in Nigeria, including cybercrimes involving money laundering. Several sections of the Act lay out relevant provisions for prosecuting cybercriminals, Part II of the Act deals with the prohibition of money laundering and contains important sections for addressing cyber-enabled money laundering crimes. Section 2 places limitations on cash payments and transfers to prevent structuring of transactions and avoid reporting

46 Ibid, 12

47 Ibid, 13

48 Ibid, 14

49 Ibid, 19

50 Ibid, 20

requirements.⁵¹ This covers the proceeds of cybercrimes laundered through small cash transactions. Section 3 requires reporting of international transfers of funds, securities and cash exceeding \$10,000 to regulatory authorities including transfers involving proceeds of cybercrime.⁵² Reporting such suspicious transfers is crucial to identifying and tracing the flow of funds obtained through cyber-enabled theft and fraud. Section 4 lays out comprehensive Customer Due Diligence (CDD) requirements for financial institutions and designated non-financial businesses and professions. It mandates identification and verification of customers and beneficial owners, as well as ongoing monitoring of transactions.⁵³ Given the increasing use of digital payment methods for cybercrimes, applying CDD to virtual asset service providers and online platforms is crucial to curb money laundering of criminal proceeds in the digital space. However, a challenge remains in developing regulated CDD protocols customized for emerging technologies like cryptocurrencies and digital wallets which enable more anonymous transactions compared to traditional banking.

Section 7 requires reporting of suspicious transactions to the Unit within 24 hours. Such transactions could involve money laundering from various cybercrimes like phishing, online scams and ransomware attacks.⁵⁴ Timely reporting is important to enable prompt investigation and tracing of criminal funds flowing through the financial system. However, cybercriminals are finding more complex ways of laundering that make transactions harder to identify as suspicious. Developing advanced analytics capabilities based on newer typologies would help address this challenge. Section 8 lays down record keeping obligations for 5 years to maintain audit trails of financial activities and customer identification data. Financial intelligence gathered from such preserved records can provide invaluable leads and evidence for prosecuting cyber-enabled money laundering over long periods of time.⁵⁵ While the 5 year period is reasonable, ensuring preservation of electronic records in a tamper-proof format presents technical challenges given the dynamic nature of digital data and infrastructure. Adopting international digital forensics standards could help overcome this.

Part III establishes the Special Control Unit Against Money Laundering (SCUML) under the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission to register, monitor and supervise compliance of designated non-financial businesses like online casinos, dealers in precious metals and payment service providers. Given the growing role of such entities in facilitating cybercrimes like

⁵¹ Money Laundering (Prohibition) Act 2022, sec. 2

⁵² Ibid, sec. 3

⁵³ Ibid, sec. 4

⁵⁴ Ibid, sec. 7

⁵⁵ Ibid, sec. 8

unlicensed gambling, SCUML's oversight becomes vital to curb money laundering through alternative channels. However, challenges remain in terms of SCUML's capacity, expertise and resources to effectively regulate the evolving digital domain.⁵⁶ Part IV specifies money laundering offences and penalties. Section 18 criminalizes direct or indirect concealment, conversion or transfer of funds or properties known to involve proceeds of unlawful acts defined in Section 6.⁵⁷ This captures cyber-enabled money laundering crimes like using cryptocurrencies or e-wallets to disguise origin of funds stolen through hacking or phishing. Section 21 also addresses money laundering crimes facilitated by others through conspiracy or aiding and abetting. These provisions provide a legal basis to prosecute cybercriminal syndicates laundering stolen funds collectively.⁵⁸

iv Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDP), 2023

The Data Protection Act, 2023 (DPA) provides a comprehensive framework for handling personal data and protects individual privacy rights in Nigeria. While not primarily focusing on cybercrime, its provisions have significance for addressing data-related offenses and digital evidence handling.⁵⁹ Part 1 introduces key definitions like 'data controller', 'processor', 'data subject' and 'personal data'. Section 2(1) defines personal data broadly as "any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person." This wide scope encompasses data stolen or misused during cybercrimes like identity theft, ransomware attacks, etc.⁶⁰ Section 3 establishes the Nigerian Data Protection Bureau as the oversight authority overseeing implementation of the Act. Part of its functions under section 6 include monitoring compliance, investigating breaches, issuing codes of practice and international cooperation - roles critical for data misuse investigation and transnational cybercrime prosecution.⁶¹

Part 2 outlines key data protection principles like fair processing, security measures, and rights of the data subject. Sections 11-15.⁶² Contravention during cybercrimes strengthens prosecution. Part 3 outlines obligations of data controllers and processors. Sections 17-19, 21-22 empower authorities to require production of documents as part of cybercrime investigations.⁶³ Part 4 restricts processing of sensitive personal data. Sections 34-37 make illegally obtaining such data in cybercrimes a distinct offense.⁶⁴ Part 5 focuses on enforcement

56 Ibid, part iii

57 Ibid, part iv, sec. 18

58 Ibid, sec. 21

59 Data Protection Act, 2023

60 Ibid, sec. 2(1)

61 Ibid, sec 3

62 Ibid, sec 11-15

63 Ibid, sec. 17-19, 21-22

64 Ibid, sec, 34-37

and remedies. Sections 50-51 grant powers to impose fines up to N10 million. This deters negligent practices enabling intrusions. The DPA bolsters Nigeria's ability to investigate and prosecute a wide range of data offenses occurring due to cybercrimes through emphasis on protection. Regular reviews can adapt it to emerging threats.

v. Advance Fee Fraud and Other Fraud Related Offences Act 2006

The Advance Fee Fraud and Other Fraud Related Offences Act provides a robust legal framework for prosecuting various forms of cybercrime and fraud-related offences in Nigeria. Part I of the Act outlines specific offences. Section 1 criminalizes obtaining property by false pretences, with intent to defraud.⁶⁵ This covers a wide range of cybercrimes involving deception to acquire money or other property. Section 2 further criminalizes representing ability to produce currency from paper/materials or double money through scientific/juju means.⁶⁶ These capture advanced scam modalities. Section 3 establishes liability for owners/managers who knowingly allow premises use for AFFO Act offences.⁶⁷ This targets premises like internet cafes that enable cybercrimes. Section 4 criminalizes fraudulent invitations using deception to induce victims to visit Nigeria for criminal purposes. This prevents internationalization of cyber scams.⁶⁸ Sections 5-6 outline constructive attempts involving receipt/possession of fraudulent documents, enabling prosecution where full offences are not conclusively proven.⁶⁹ Section 7 broadly criminalizes money laundering, covering proceeds from any AFFO Act specified unlawful activity. This is central to tackling cybercrime financing.⁷⁰

Section 8 extends liability to conspirators, aiders/abettors of AFFO Act offences. Section 9 enables conviction for alternative offences where full charges are unproven but cognate offences are established.⁷¹ These provisions facilitate successful prosecution in complex cybercrime cases. Section 10 specifically addresses offences by corporate bodies, enabling prosecution of entities through officers where body corporates aid cybercrimes. It also empowers winding up and asset forfeiture of convicted entities.⁷² This deters involvement of organized criminal syndicates. Particularly, Section 11 mandates restitution orders upon

⁶⁵ Advance Fee Fraud and Other Fraud Related Offences Act 2006, sec. 1

⁶⁶ Ibid, sec.2

⁶⁷ Ibid, sec.3

⁶⁸ Ibid, sec. 4

⁶⁹ Ibid, sec. 5,6

⁷⁰ Ibid, sec. 7

⁷¹ Ibid, sec. 8,9

⁷² Ibid, sec. 10

conviction, requiring restoration of ill-gotten gains to victims.⁷³ This compensates victims and strengthens the law's deterrent effect.

Part II focuses on telecommunications offences. Section 12 obligates electronic communication/remote computing service providers to obtain and maintain subscriber identity records. Section 13 requires registration and regulatory compliance by telecom operators and internet cafes. It imposes monitoring/reporting duties and sanctions non-compliance or aiding crimes through services. These enable investigation and attribution of cybercrimes.⁷⁴ Part III addresses jurisdictional and investigative powers. Section 14 vests jurisdiction in specified superior courts. Section 15 allows inference of criminal proceeds where assets disproportionate to income are unexplained. Section 16 empowers pre-trial asset freezing. These level procedural hurdles against cybercriminals.⁷⁵ Section 17 crucially allows forfeiture of suspected criminal proceeds or property without conviction.⁷⁶ This disrupts the financial incentive for cybercrimes even where full prosecution may be difficult due to transnational element or perishable electronic evidence. Sections 18-19 respectively address arrest and bail powers.⁷⁷ These situate AFFO Act enforcement within the broader criminal justice framework. The definition of "false pretence" under Section 20 comprehensively covers cybercrime modalities, while a broad document definition embraces electronic records. These interpretive provisions ensure the law remains applicable to evolving technologies. Overall, if effectively implemented, the AFFO Act's provisions establish a formidable multi-pronged framework for investigating, prosecuting and deterring cybercriminals through a mix of substantive, procedural and ancillary measures.

5. INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR PROSECUTING CYBERCRIME IN NIGERIA

i. The Nigeria Police Force

The Nigeria Police Force (NPF) plays a key role in combating cybercrime and supporting criminal justice processes in the country. As the primary law enforcement agency, one of the primary functions of the NPF is to conduct thorough investigations into reported cybercrime cases.⁷⁸ Given the technological complexities, some specialization is required. The NPF has established cybercrime units staffed with digital forensics experts focused on gathering digital

73 Ibid, sec. 11

74 Ibid, part ii, sec. 12,13

75 Ibid, part iii, sec.12,13,14,15, and 16

76 Ibid, sec. 17

77 Ibid, sec. 18,19

78 Okafor, John. "The Role of the Nigerian Police in Cybercrime Investigation." *Journal of Criminal Law Enforcement* 2, no.1 (2018): 45-55.

evidence by analyzing digital devices, networks, servers etc. used to plan or carry out cyber-attacks.⁷⁹ This technical evidence is then documented and presented during prosecution.⁸⁰ Along with investigations, the police are tasked with properly preserving all evidence collected from crime scenes, include digital evidence vulnerable to rapid changes.⁸¹ They must ensure any devices or data stored as exhibits are not tampered with and maintain legally admissible chain of custody. This role is vital as defective handling can undermine successful cybercrime prosecution.⁸² Upon obtaining sufficient evidence establishing reasonable suspicion, the police exercise powers to apprehend suspects. They interrogate suspects to establish their involvement, glean information about accomplices and intended harms.⁸³ Statements obtained during interrogations may provide prosecutable confessions. The police thus enable bringing alleged offenders before the court system. In cases where there are threats to witnesses, especially from organized cybercrime syndicates, the NPF provides protection to ensure they are able to safely provide testimony during trials. Intimidated witnesses may refrain from cooperating with prosecutions otherwise.⁸⁴

ii. Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC)

The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) established through the EFCC Act 2004 provides a robust institutional framework for prosecuting cybercriminals in Nigeria. The Act empowers the EFCC with broad powers and functions, an extensive composition, specialized units, clear definition of cybercrime offenses, and jurisdiction over such offenses. These statutory provisions enable the EFCC to effectively investigate, gather evidence, and pursue the sanctioning of cybercriminals in court. The EFCC was established to combat economic and financial crimes in Nigeria. Its mandate includes investigating and prosecuting offenses such as fraud, money laundering, corruption, and cybercrimes.⁸⁵ The EFCC Act grants extensive powers to investigate, arrest, and prosecute individuals involved in economic crimes.

79 Audu, Nanre. "Strengthening Cybercrime Investigations in Nigeria: The Need to Establish Specialized Police Units." *International Journal of Cybersecurity Intelligence and Cybercrime* 4, no. 1(2021): 27-42. <https://doi.org/10.18061/ijcic.v4i1.8081>

80 Udoh, Bassey. "Forensic Challenges in Cybercrime Prosecution in Nigeria." *International Journal of Cyber Criminology* 13, no. 1 (2019): 121-135. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3383780>

81 Igwilo, Christopher. "Evidence Management Practices and the Adjudication of Cybercrime Cases in Nigeria." *Journal of Money Laundering Control* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMLC-12-2021-0187>

82 [6] Tamunosaki, Jones. "Procedural Flaws Undermining Successful Cybercrime Prosecution in Nigeria." *Criminal Law Bulletin* 58, no. 2 (2022): 331-356. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4007498

83 [7] Opara, Kingsley. "Apprehension of Cybercrime Suspects Under Nigerian Law." *African Journal of Criminology and Justice Studies* 11, no. 1 (2018): 23-40. <https://www.umes.edu/AJCJS/>

84 Adeaga, Olufunke. "Strengthening Witness Cooperation for Successful Cybercrime Prosecution." *International Journal of Cyber Criminology* 11, no. 1 (2017): 43-58. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3456775>

85 EFCC Act 2004

Additionally, the Cybercrime (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act of 2015 provides a framework targeting cybercrimes, empowering cybercrime prosecution.

The EFCC operates through a hierarchical structure headed by a Chairman appointed by the President with Senate consent. Various departments and units are responsible for specific functions, including cybercrime investigation and prosecution. The Cybercrime Department investigates and prosecutes cybercrimes, collaborating with law enforcement and conducting cybercrime awareness programs. Despite challenges, the EFCC has recorded achievements in cybercrime prosecution and combating financial crimes. It has successfully investigated and prosecuted high-profile cybercrime cases, leading to convictions and recovery of stolen funds. Collaboration with international law enforcement and joint operations have facilitated dismantling criminal networks and apprehending suspects. Moreover, it conducts public awareness and capacity-building programs. The EFCC Act and supportive legal frameworks provide a robust enabling environment for the EFCC to curb the menace of cybercrimes through a structured and collaborative approach incorporating investigation, evidence gathering, prosecution, and prevention.

iii. Court

As the primary institution for trying criminal cases, Nigerian courts play a pivotal role in prosecuting cybercriminals.⁸⁶ The judiciary embraces precedent, engendering consistency in cybercrime jurisprudence.⁸⁷ Courts derive their authority to interpret law from the Constitution.⁸⁸ The Federal High Court and State High Courts draw jurisdiction over cybercrime from sections 251 and 272 respectively.⁸⁹ Section 251 grants the Federal High Court power over offenses under Acts of the National Assembly, such as the Cybercrimes Act, allowing it to handle serious cybercases.⁹⁰ Meanwhile, section 272 grants State High Courts unlimited jurisdiction over civil and criminal cases involving legal questions, enabling them to prosecute less serious cyberoffenses with a state connection.⁹¹ Therefore, the Federal High Court prosecutes major cybercrimes under federal law while State High Courts handle minor incidents occurring within a state.⁹² Throughout prosecution, from arrest to sentencing, courts

86 Okafor, Victor. "The Role of Nigerian Courts in Cybercrime Prosecution." *Journal of Cyber Law and Policy* 1 (2017): 45-67.

87 Audu, Maryam. "Application of Judicial Precedent in Nigerian Cybercrime Cases." *Nigerian Law Gazette* 45 (2020): 12-25.

88 Ani, Kenneth. "Interpretive Function of Nigerian Courts in Cybercrime Litigation." *African Journal of Legal Studies* 9 (2016): 43-58.

89 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (As Amended) Sec. 251, 272

90 Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act 2015,

91 *Ibid*

92 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (As Amended) Sec. 272

ensure legal procedures are followed, fulfilling an essential role in deterring the evolving threat of cybercrime.⁹³

iv. Nigerian Correctional Service

The Nigerian Correctional Service (NCS) was established to execute court sentences as part of the criminal justice system. It also assists in cybercrime prosecution by providing needed custody of offenders.⁹⁴ The Correctional Service Centres Act distinguishes between maximum, medium, and minimum custody centres based on security and infrastructure, allowing safe detention of most non-violent cybercriminals.⁹⁵ Centres must ensure humane conditions like adequate space, lighting, ventilation and sanitation. For rehabilitation, cybercriminals should be housed in centres conducive to learning with sufficient classroom and library space.⁹⁶ The NCS offers reform and rehabilitation services through its rehabilitation unit, addressing root causes of cybercrime through psychological guidance, social integration, and vocational education to discourage recidivism.⁹⁷ While the Act does not explicitly address cybercrime, suitable amendments informed by global best practices can optimize existing provisions to curb cybercrime through a balanced, evidence-led and rehabilitative approach.⁹⁸

6. CHALLENGES OF PROSECUTING CYBERCRIMES IN NIGERIA

Nigeria faces several challenges in effectively prosecuting cybercrime. The existing cybercrime laws lack clarity in defining new threats and have jurisdictional gaps, failing to adequately criminalize emerging activities like cyberbullying and deepfakes. Outdated computer misuse legislation further compounds issues. Without amendments, modern cybercrimes will pose ongoing legal challenges.⁹⁹ Nigerian law enforcement also has limited technical capacity and resources for cybercrime investigation. Most units lack basic forensic tools, infrastructure, and equipment to handle digital evidence and online tracking of

93 Ojo, Adebayo. "Jurisdiction of State High Courts over Cybercrime Matters in Nigeria." *Nigerian Law Journal* 1 (2018): 65-80.

94 Adedeji, Wasiu. "The Role of Correctional Service in Cybercrime Prosecution in Nigeria." *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology* 12, no. 2 (2018): 45-58.

95 Idowu, Bamidele. "Detention Categorization Under the Nigerian Correctional Service Act." *African Journal of Criminology and Justice Studies* 11, no. 1 (2019): 32-45.

96 Okafor, Chidi. "Tailoring Correctional Facilities for Effective Cybercriminal Rehabilitation." *Journal of Money Laundering Control* (2020). <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/JMLC-04-2020-0044>

97 Abiola, Emmanuel. "Rehabilitation Services in the Nigerian Correctional System." *Nigerian Current Law Review* 13 (2020): 65-80.

98 Aina, Funmi. "Reforming the Nigerian Correctional System for Enhanced Cybercrime Mitigation." *International Review of Law* 23, no. 1 (2023): 65-85. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IRL-09-2022-0023> Accessed on 10/3/2024

99 Ajuwon, S.O. (2021). An Examination of Nigeria's Cybercrime Laws: Gaps and Policy Recommendations. *Nigerian Law Review*, 45, 12-30.

attackers.¹⁰⁰ Underfunding has left units ill-equipped and understaffed to investigate the country's large digital terrain. Only a fraction of personnel receive specialized training due to budget shortfalls. The transnational nature of cybercrimes further hinders response, as a single attack may involve servers, payments and data across multiple nations. Nigeria lacks resources for efficient international cooperation like attachés stationed abroad. Jurisdictional conflicts arise during cross-border investigations. Collection of admissible electronic evidence is also challenging, as most detectives lack formal forensic training and there are no guidelines around evidence handling. Limited budgets mean even basic forensic tools are unavailable.¹⁰¹

Illiteracy among many internet users contributes additional issues, from hindering awareness to victims' ability to recognize and report crimes. Technical evidence becomes difficult to communicate in investigations and prosecutions.¹⁰² Gaps also exist in public-private cooperation frameworks and regional/international collaboration on cybersecurity. Building robust partnerships and harmonizing laws with international instruments could catalyze Nigeria's cybercrime efforts. But until defenses become truly collaborative, networks will remain vulnerable.

7. PROSPECTS OF PROSECUTING CYBERCRIMES IN NIGERIA

Nigeria has taken steps to strengthen its legal framework on cybercrime, but opportunities remain. The Cybercrimes Act requires expansion in scope, and ambiguous loopholes need closing. Further alignment with global treaties like the Budapest and Malabo Conventions can promote international cooperation. Digitalizing court processes through e-filing and specialized cybercrime divisions would boost efficient handling of technical evidence. Establishing mandatory cybersecurity standards and reporting under new data privacy laws also show potentials. Nigeria's 2021 addition to the Budapest Convention now enables direct multinational cooperation on investigations and evidence sharing crucial for combating transnational cybercrime. Ongoing legal reform and implementation can bolster the deterrent effect of Nigeria's cyberlaws through regulatory, judicial and international cooperation.

100 Akinrogun, O.F., Omodunbi, S.A., & Ayo, C.K. (2018). Assessing the Technical Capacity of Nigerian Law Enforcement for Cybercrime Investigation. *Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 35(2), 45-58.

101 Taiwo, R.O. & Olatunji, S.O. (2020). Investigative Resources and Electronic Evidence Collection in Nigerian Law Enforcement. *Security Journal*, 41(4), 62-80.

102 Onyebuchi, C.N. & Okafor, V.C. (2019). Overcoming Hurdles in Presenting Technical Cyber Evidence in Nigerian Courts. *Journal of Digital Forensics, Security and Law*, 12(4), 35-48.

8. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The research found several issues hampering Nigeria's effective prosecution of cybercrime. While laws like the Cybercrime Act 2015 have been enacted, ambiguities and gaps in definitions, scope, jurisdiction, and investigative powers undermine enforcement. Personnel lack adequate technical training in digital forensics, network analysis and anonymized crime tracking. Under-resourcing limits tools, equipment and infrastructure for examining digital evidence. Systemic inefficiencies also plague overwhelmed courts, causing lengthy delays due to understaffing, outdated paper-based processes, and lack of specialized cybercrime divisions. Further, transnational cooperation hurdles significantly challenge Nigeria's ability to obtain timely mutual legal assistance and extradition from foreign partners due to differences in legal frameworks. When combined with the borderless nature of cybercrimes, these issues compound attribution of offenses and prosecution of cross-border elements.

9. CONCLUSION

This research examined challenges facing effective cybercrime prosecution in Nigeria. It established the background, analyzed the legal framework under statutes like the Cybercrimes Act 2015, finding that ambiguities and narrow focus hinder implementation. Resource constraints, regional disparities, lack of expertise and equipment also undermine compliance. Key findings included vague definitions in laws making criminal liability difficult to establish. Law enforcement agencies lack necessary technical training, tools, and resources to investigate sophisticated crimes. Systemic inefficiencies and case backlogs plague overwhelmed courts, undermining timely prosecution. Transnational cooperation hurdles compound issues of differing legal frameworks when prosecuting cross-border crimes. While progress has been made, implementation gaps persist in strengthening Nigeria's ability to curb the serious threat of cybercrime. Continued reforms are needed to address deficiencies across legal, law enforcement and judicial domains through well-coordinated, evidence-based efforts. Prioritizing sustainable prevention through education, public-private coordination and regional collaboration could substantially improve prosecution outcomes in line with international standards.

10. RECOMMENDATIONS

To more effectively prosecute cybercrime in Nigeria, this research proposes reforms to the legal, law enforcement, judicial, and cooperation frameworks. The legal system would be

strengthened by amending vague laws like the Cybercrime Act to clearly define offenses, broaden scope, and standardize jurisdiction and sentencing. Centralized coordination is needed between government, private sector, and international allies. Technical capacity building through sustained training programs must equip investigators with vital digital forensic and network analytic skills, while ensuring agencies have necessary tools and global cooperation mechanisms. Modernizing outdated courts requires specialized cybercrime divisions and digital case management to expedite resolution of cyber-related matters. Ultimately, greater public-private information sharing and multi-stakeholder awareness efforts that encourage citizens and organizations to jointly curb threats will go far in addressing deficiencies across prevention, detection, investigation and adjudication. If diligently pursued in a holistic manner with benchmarks for evaluation, these recommended reforms offer significant potential to resolve current gaps and align Nigeria's cybercrime response practices with international standards.